

BILINGUAL EDUCATION AS ONE OF THE INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS

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Annotation: At present, a new education system is being formed, focused on entering the world educational space. This process is accompanied by significant changes in the pedagogical theory and practice of the educational process. There is a change in the educational paradigm: different content, different transitions, different law, different attitudes, different behavior, different pedagogical mentality are offered.

This article analyzes the information about the innovative approach of the bilingual education method and its effectiveness in teaching English.

Key words: Teaching materials, bilingual education, innovative materials, pedagogy, development of language, methodology, methods.

Education systems are considered in the last 50 years the existence of two languages and even the focus on bilingualism has spread throughout the world. The main reason, of course, is the increasing interdependence of countries to force the knowledge and use of foreign languages and converting some languages into international tools communication, on the other hand, the desire to preserve the original language and culture of peoples. Information trends have spread across the globe, leading to the emergence of a new type of education - bilingual education.

The inevitable and sudden spread of bilingual education faces great challenges and both in connection with its pedagogical organization, and acute problems related to determining the goals and evaluating the results. When creating a bilingual education system, first of all, it is necessary to determine its language the purpose and role assigned to each language as a language of instruction, the level of proficiency students are expected to achieve in each language and the situations in which they are expected uses. Like all policy decisions, these decisions about the language goals of education should also be informed by language planning in any country.

Later, psychological, pedagogical and organizational problems of bilingual education appear and are solved after a serious scientific understanding of the particular situation build on knowledge and critical analysis of previous work.

The educational content is enriched through the development of new procedural skills, the ability to work with information, creative problem solving of science and market practice, attention to the individualization of educational programs. Traditional ways of informing - oral and written speech, telephone radio communication - are giving way to computer teaching aids, telecommunication networks for use on a global scale. The most important component of the pedagogical process is the student-oriented interaction of the teacher with the students. The role of science in the creation of pedagogical technologies corresponding to the level of public knowledge is growing.

At the same time, it is necessary to organize a kind of dialogue between different pedagogical systems and teaching technologies, to test new forms in practice - additional alternatives to the state education system, to create a holistic pedagogy of the past in modern Russian conditions. It is important to use systems. In such a situation, the teacher should take a broad approach to modern innovative technologies, ideas, schools, directions, and not waste time discovering the known. One of these innovative technologies is bilingual education, the essence and mechanisms of which we will consider below.

The problem of the native language always arises in the development of foreign language teaching methods. The complexity of this problem is reflected in the popular methodological principles of teaching, such as relying on the native language, taking it into account or excluding it from the educational process. And so far, no power decisions can change the real state of affairs: all speech mechanisms of students are formed and work in their native language and reflect the national view of the surrounding reality. As a result, the student associate's new lexemes not with objects of reality, but with the words of his native language, taking the first steps towards mastering a foreign speech through his native language.

At the initial stages of training, a subordinate type of bilingualism is created. And only later, with a higher level of language proficiency, does a consistent bilingualism begin to form with two conceptual bases, each of which is associated with one language. This is an objective process, and the solution to the problem of the native language should be sought in the formation of the mechanism of bilingualism.

At present, the data of physiology allow us to draw a fairly well-reasoned conclusion that mastering a second language is not just the accumulation of linguistic material as a result of the selection of lexical units, situations and the assimilation of grammatical forms and structures, but the restructuring of human speech mechanisms for interaction, and later and the parallel use of two language systems, which at the first stages of language acquisition requires the formation of the skill of switching from language to language, and at later stages, the neutralization of one system in order to create more favorable conditions for the functioning of the other system.

That is why, when teaching a foreign language, the creation of a bilingualism mechanism should be considered the primary task of the methodology. The essence of the mechanism of bilingualism lies in the excitation of sign, denotative or situational connections of lexical units in the conditions of the need or the possibility of choosing between two language systems. When studying the lexical units of the second language, regardless of the method of teaching, each new foreign language lexical unit that appears in the student's field of vision is associated not with one or another subject of reality, but with the corresponding word of the native language and only through it with the designated one. In this case, there is a danger of creating false sign relationships in the event that a new foreign word does not have a full-fledged equivalent in the native language.

Verbal accuracy exercises and the use of subjective words as a learning tool have not yet found wide application, with the exception of teaching interpretation in translation faculties. Meanwhile, their effectiveness in creating a mechanism for bilingualism has long been proven by the practice of teaching in a number of higher educational institutions. The process of creating a bilingual mechanism is not limited to the listed teaching methods. This will also be facilitated by exercises aimed at the formation of accompanying speech

mechanisms. These exercises include: repetition of a foreign language text, which changes according to the pace of speech over a certain period of time; various types of tongue twisters in the target language, intralinguistic translation (transmission of the same content by various means of the native language); listening to a foreign text based on the text in the native language; difficulty hearing; visual perception of text with an account and some others.

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